

Possible Antiparkinsonian Compounds-Part V : Synthesis of Some Piperazine-1,4-Bis-(2-Methyl-4-Arylidene-5-Oxo-Imidazoliny)-1-Alkyl Carboxylates

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A few piperazine-bis-salts of 2-methyl-4-arylidene-5-oxo-imidazoliny-1-alkyl carboxylic acids have been synthesised with a view to evaluate their antiparkinsonian and other central nervous system activities.

IMIDAZOLONES have been reported to be active as anticonvulsants¹⁻⁴, sedatives and hypnotics⁵ and as monoamine oxidase inhibitors^{2,8}. Lower amino acids like γ -amino-butyric acid, β -alanine and glycine have been described to be inhibitory neurotransmitters^{6,7}. According to Woert and Hadzovic⁸, and Geigy⁹, the lower amino acids and their derivatives have been found very effective in antagonising the parkinsonian symptoms. Anticonvulsant activity of β -alanine and γ -amino butyric acid and few other simple carboxylic acids and their derivatives has been reported by Kazunichi¹⁰, Ostasz¹¹, Schwartz et al¹² and Ferrari¹³. These valid observations led us to synthesise imidazolonyl-1-alkyl carboxylic acids as the tertiary amide derivatives of glycine, β -alanine and γ -amino butyric acid. Further, piperazine derivatives have also been found active against parkinsonism and allied diseases^{13,14}. More specifically, piperazine-bis-salts have been found active in inhibiting certain parkinsonian features¹⁵. Therefore, it was worthwhile to synthesise the piperazine-bis-salts of the aforesaid 5-oxo-imidazoliny-1-yl-carboxylic acids and to test their antiparkinsonian and other CNS activities.

The synthesis was accomplished along the following route

Experimental

Acetyl glycine (I)—It was prepared by the acetylation of glycine, as described by Vogel¹⁶.

TABLE I—1-(2'-METHYL, 4'-SUBSTITUTED BENZYLIDENE-5'-OXO-IMIDAZOLINY)-ALKYL CARBOXYLIC ACID (III).

Compound No.	X ¹	X ²	m.p. °C	Yield %
n=1				
1.	-H	-H	248	60
2.	-H	-Cl	242	45
3.	-Cl	-Cl	230	50
4.	-H	-OH	240-41	40
5.	-H	-O.CH ₃	233	42
6.	-OH	-O.CH ₃	220-21	50
n=2				
7.	-H	-H	262	48
8.	-H	-Cl	224	50
9.	-Cl	-Cl	215	45
10.	-H	-OH	231-32	55
11.	-H	-O.CH ₃	235-36	60
12*	-OH	-O.CH ₃	228	55
n=3				
13*	-H	-H	258	50
14.	-H	-Cl	228-29	52
15.	-Cl	-Cl	215-16	47
16.	-H	-OH	237	57
17.	-H	-O.CH ₃	240-42	60
18*	-OH	-O.CH ₃	222	62

1. m.p. were taken in open capillaries and are uncorrected.
2. All the compounds gave correct analysis for N%.

2-Methyl, 4-substituted benzylidene-oxazolin-5-ones (II): The methods of Vogel¹⁶, Herbst and Shemin¹⁷, Dakin¹⁸ and Niender & Ziering¹⁹ have been utilised to synthesise the required oxazolin-5-ones.

1-(2'-Methyl, 4'-benzylidene-5'-oxo-imidazoliny)-acetic acid (III): 2-methyl, 4-benzylidene-oxazolin-5-one (0.02 mole) and glycine (0.02 mole) were refluxed for 10 hrs. in a mixture of pyridine (20 ml.) and water (5 ml.). The solvents were distilled off at the reduced pressure and ethyl alcohol was added to the residue and boiled on a water bath. The unreacted glycine eliminated as the solid residue. The alcohol was distilled off and the pasty mass left behind was poured in HCl (20 ml.). The residue was filtered and recrystallised from chloroform; m.p. 248°, Yield-60%; TLC (Rf values) 0.088 (Benzene/methanol 9 : 1); 0.27 (Benzene/Methanol; 8 : 2).

Other 5-oxo-imidazoliny-alkyl carboxylic acids were synthesised in a similar way and are described in Table-1.

Piperazine-1, 4-bis-[1-(2'-methyl-4'-benzylidene-5'-oxo-imidazoliny) acetate] (IV): A mixture of 1-(2'-methyl-4'-benzylidene-5'-oxo-imidazoliny), acetic acid (0.02 mole) and piperazine-hexahydrate (0.01 mole) was refluxed in absolute methanol (20 ml) for about two hours on a water bath. The reaction mixture was cooled and filtered. The solid residue was recrystallised with methanol/acetone, m.p. >280°, Yield 70%, TLC (Rf values): 0.14 (Benzene/Methanol; 8 : 2); 0.58 (100% methanol).

In a similar way, other piperazine salts of the analogous series were also synthesised. Their relevant data are given in Table-2.

Pharmacology: Fourteen compounds of the above scheme (marked by asterisks in Table 1 & 2) were subjected to the study of their effects on the CNS of albino mice of either sex. ALD_{50} was also determined to mark the toxicity in the compounds²⁰. Antiparkinsonian and analgesic activities were also done, as special screenings of compound nos. 29, 30, 31, 32 & 36.

To study the gross effects, the albino mice of either sex, weighing between 15-25 g. and grouped in four, were given the compounds (in water solution form and intraperitoneally) at the doses of 200, 400 and 800 mg/kg wt. of mice. After one hour of drug administration the effects of compound on various behavioural activities were noted all the fourteen compounds have been found to be the CNS depressants. They decreased the spontaneous motor activity and reactivity. The depression was not of permanent nature in compound nos. 12, 29, 30 and 32. This eliminated the possibility of hypnotic effect in these compounds. All the compounds induced writhing and the compound nos. 29, 32 and 36 induced straub-tail and ataxia.

TABLE 2—PIPERAZINE-1, 4-BIS-[1-(2'-METHYL-4'-SUBSTITUTED BENZYLIDENE-5'-OXO-IMIDAZOLINY)-ALKYL CARBOXYLATES] (IV).

Compound No.	X ¹	X ²	m.p. °C	Yield %
		n=1		
19.	-H	-H	280	70
20.	-H	-Cl	280	60
21*.	-Cl	-Cl	280	72
22.	-H	-OH	280	75
23*.	-H	-O.CH ₃	280	75
24.	-OH	-O.CH ₃	280	68
		n=2		
25.	-H	-H	280	60
26*.	-H	-Cl	280	72
27.	-Cl	-Cl	280	62
28.	-H	-OH	280	77
29*.	-H	-O.CH ₃	280	65
30*.	-OH	-O.CH ₃	280	70
		n=3		
31*.	-H	-H	280	60
32*.	-H	-Cl	280	62
33*.	-Cl	-Cl	280	65
34*.	-H	-OH	280	68
35*.	-H	-O.CH ₃	280	60
36*.	-OH	-O.CH ₃	280	62

1. m.p. were taken in open capillaries and are uncorrected.
2. All the compounds gave correct analysis for N%.

Mortality after 24 hrs. in 50% of animals tested, marked the ALD_{50} , which was more than 800 mg/kg wt. of mice for all compounds.

For anti-parkinsonian activity, oxotremorine hydrochloride was used as the tremorigenic substance and the method of Kerley et al²¹ was followed. None of the compounds could exhibit significant anti-tremor activity.

Analgesia was noted following the method of Smith²². The analgesia produced by compound nos. 29, 30, 31, 32 & 36 was 60%, 80%, 40%, 40% and 20% respectively.

As a result, it is noteworthy that compound nos. 36, 31, 32, 29 and 30 have muscle relaxant properties in an increasing order.

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